

Directional Probability in the Macroscopic World and Quantum Mechanics

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Newtonian mechanics is deterministic and deals with specific directions in space, i.e. velocity and acceleration have specific directions. Probability also exists in the Newtonian world in at least two forms. The first is the die/coin toss or random number generator and the second is of the form of $P(x)dx = \text{constant}$ for constant velocity or $P(x)dx = Cdx/v$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ (nonrelativistic) and other similar probabilities. The problem with the latter is that it is not directional and so may not be directly applicable to a directional motion probabilistic problem. In fact, $P(x)dx = dx/L$ ($L = \text{length}$) contains both p and $-p$, we argue, i.e. $P(x)dx = Pd(p,x)Pd(-p,x) dx$ where $Pd(p,x)$ is a dynamical probability. We suggest that it is a directional dynamical probability Pd whose information is linked with the dynamical variable p . Both are needed to solve dynamical probabilistic problems (i.e. problems which have a direction).

Another classical probability which is not directional is: $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ ((1)). This equation holds for one dimensional reflection/refraction. The issue is that ((1)) does not reflect the direction of motion. In what sense does it not reflect the direction of motion? One may immediately note that momentum and its direction is not present in ((1)), but it may be introduced by writing: $\text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) = AA / c$, where A is flux and c , the speed of light. Using $E=pc$, one may replace $1/c$ with $E/c = p$. Thus, one might argue that one may bring in directionality. We note, however, that directionality is a piece of information and according to information theory $\ln(\text{Probability}) = \text{information}$. In this sense, AA/c does not yield information directly. To bring back momentum, a dynamical variable, one would need a probability of the form $\exp(p)$, for example. In other words, one requires that dynamical variables such as E , p in Newtonian mechanics appear as information. This cannot happen with Newtonian probability which is a constant, e.g. $P(x) = Pd(p,x) Pd(-p,x) = \text{constant}$ because $P(x)$ contains both p and $-p$ information, we argue. One needs to use $Pd(p,x)$ which is a dynamical probability and this, we argue, is at least one situation in which quantum mechanics appears. The example of one dimensional photon reflection/refraction seems to be based solely on the idea of directional probability and not on size. No use of Planck's constant is needed. Even though a photon is small and so are the molecules with which it interacts, the reflection/refraction problem, which exists in the macroscopic world (light and a window) makes no use of small sizes, but only of directional probability whose information yields dynamical, directional variables, e.g. p .

Solving One Dimensional Reflection/Refraction By Splitting Classical Probability into Two Equations

One may formally solve the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem to obtain the results of (1) without what may seem like any use of directional probability. One may begin with:

$$1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract}) \quad ((2))$$

One may next write probability as: AA/c where AA is flux and c , the speed of light in medium i . One may also use $E=pc$ and not that E is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted photon. Thus:

$$AA/c - BB/c = CC/c^2 \quad ((3)) \quad AA=\text{incident flux, } BB \text{ reflected and } CC \text{ refracted}$$

One may then use a “math trick” , i.e. the difference of squares, to obtain the two required equations needed to solve for the two unknowns B,C assuming A is known, i.e.

$$A + B = C \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad Ap - pB = Cp^2 \quad ((4b)) \quad \text{where } p^2 = p_1^2, n^2 = \text{index of refraction.}$$

One may then solve ((4a)) and ((4b)) for B/A and C/A and obtain the results of ((1)).

We argue, however, that using differences of squares to solve this problem is not really a math trick. One may note that ((4b)) contains a dynamical variable p , and A,B,C which are square root fluxes (linked with square root probabilities). If one examines ((4a)) and ((4b)), it appears that p, p^2 are pieces of information associated with the probabilities and that ((4b)) may be obtained from ((4a)) using a math operator. In fact, (1) uses the notion of an electric field of the form $\cos(-\omega t + px)$ and insists on the field and its first derivative being continuous at $x=0$. Hence, the math operator is d/dx in (1).

We suggest that in information theory, $\ln(\text{probability}) = \text{information}$ and that the dynamic variable p is information. The problem is that even though probability exists in Newtonian dynamics, it is not directional and so cannot yield p . For example:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x) \quad \text{where} \quad .5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{nonrelativistic} \quad ((5))$$

$P(x)$ cannot be biased and so describes both p and $-p$ at the same time, i.e.

$$P(x) = Pd(p,x) Pd(-p,x) \quad ((6))$$

Here $Pd(p,x)$ is a biased, dynamical probability containing information about p . In such a case, one may require that:

$$\ln(Pd(p,x)) \quad \text{yield information about } p \quad ((7))$$

Given that there is translational invariance, we suggest that d/dx is an translational generator such that:

$$d/dx \ln(Pd(p,x)) = p \quad \text{or} \quad Pd(p,x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

Thus, we argue that the difference of squares trick is really equivalent to formulating the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem in terms of dynamic probabilities.

Recap of Newtonian Mechanics and Probability

The one dimensional reflection-refraction problem requires the use of probability. We suggest that this is not of the form of a probability generator at each collision of a photon with a molecule because E is constant for the incident, reflected and refracted photon, and the refracted photon seems to move smoothly in the n_2 material. Thus, probability seems to apply throughout space. Newtonian mechanics yields a probability: $P(x)dx = \text{constant } dx$ for constant p , but this contains both p and $-p$, i.e. is not directional.

We suggest that this macroscopic problem requires a probability which contains direction, i.e. p as information. Such a probability does not seem to exist in Newtonian mechanics, but rather must be derived from it using the above ideas. Thus, $P_d(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ satisfies two criteria:

- (A) It represents a kind of probability needed for probabilistic problems
- (B) It contains a dynamic variable from Newtonian mechanics, p , which is also needed and this variable is linked with information, i.e. $\ln(P_d)$.

Thus, instead of deterministic directional Newtonian mechanics which uses E , p , one has directional probabilities which also use E , p (e.g. $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$).

Conclusion

In conclusion, Newtonian mechanics deals with important information such as p , E and direction in a directional, deterministic manner. Newtonian mechanics can also handle probability in the form of $P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the magnitude of velocity. We suggest that $P(x)$ has a shortcoming in that it does not describe directional motion. For example, for $v(x)=\text{constant}$, $P(x)=\text{constant}$, i.e. the amount of time in each dx is the same dt value. This applies to p and $-p$ (or v and $-v$). It is clear, however, that p and $-p$ do not appear explicitly, in $P(x)$, but appear in Newtonian dynamics. We suggest that actually they do appear in $P(x)$, but in the following manner: $P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$, i.e. $P(x)$ is a product of two dynamic probabilities P_d . It is the dynamic probability which contains information about p (i.e. direction), but is also probabilistic. In particular, $P_d(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ so that $d/dx \ln(P_d(p,x)) = p$. In other words, quantum mechanics provides directional unusual probabilities which contain information about dynamical variables needed to solve a probabilistic, dynamical/directional problem.

Thus, we note that Newtonian mechanics may be used to solve a directional non-probabilistic problem using variables p and E . These same variables may be needed in a probabilistic problem which must then contain direction as well. We suggest that it is the quantum mechanical directional (dynamical) probability $P_d(p,x)$ which is required in such a case. The example of one dimensional reflection-refraction is a case in point. Even though a photon is tiny as are the molecules in the medium with index of refraction n_2 , it seems that the problem may be solved completely using directional probability, i.e. $A+B = C$ and $pA - pB = p^2 C$ where $p^2 = n_2^2 p$. Planck's constant does not appear anywhere in this result which applies to the macroscopic world.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change